

Biologically active flavonoids and saponins from the genus *Chenopodium*

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Abstract

This review summarizes the current knowledge of biologically active flavonoids and saponins from the genus *Chenopodium*. Information was gathered through comprehensive searches of leading scientific databases, including Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar, covering literature up to March 2026. The article provides a detailed analysis of the biological activities of 55 compounds (25 flavonoids and 30 saponins) isolated from various species of the genus (*C. album*, *C. ambrosioides*, *C. quinoa*, *C. formosanum*, *C. murale*, *C. ficifolium*, *C. foliosum*, *C. bonus-henricus*, and *C. strictum*). Where available, correlations between chemical structure and bioactivity are discussed, and quantitative data are also presented. These compounds display diverse biological activities, including antioxidant and cellular protection, metabolic regulation (anti-adipogenic, prolipase, and anti- α -glucosidase), neuro- and cardioprotection, hepatoprotection, antimicrobial effects, and immunomodulatory and cytotoxic properties. This review is intended to inspire focused research on *Chenopodium* flavonoids and saponins, advancing the development of natural product therapies for major human diseases.

Keywords

biological activities, *Chenopodium*, flavonoids, saponins

Introduction

Plants have long played a fundamental role in human civilization, serving not only as sources of food and raw materials but also as essential components of traditional medicine systems across cultures (Elshafie et al. 2023). The genus *Chenopodium* (Amaranthaceae) comprises more than 200 species with a wide global distribution. Many of these species have traditionally been used as supplementary grains, leafy vegetables, and medicinal plants in various traditional healthcare systems (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2009).

The economically important goosefoot species include *C. album*, *C. berlandieri* subsp. *nuttalliae*, *C. pallidicaule*, and *C. quinoa* (Bhargava et al. 2005): *C. quinoa* is valued for its seeds used as flour, spinach-like leaves, and edible sprouts; *C. pallidicaule* (Cañihua) is cultivated in Peru and Bolivia for seeds used in soups, flour, and fermented foods; *C. berlandieri* subsp. *nuttalliae* produces Huauzontle, Quelite, and Chia roja; while *C. album* is mainly grown for its leaves, although some Himalayan cultivars also yield grain (Nedialkov and Kokanova-Nedialkova 2021).

Different *Chenopodium* species have long been used in folk medicine for preventing and treating various diseases. *C. bonus-henricus* (wild spinach) is consumed as a vegetable in several European countries, while in Bulgaria, its root extracts (“chuyen”) treat respiratory, rheumatic, gastrointestinal, and skin disorders and are used in traditional foods such as tahini and white halva (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017, 2019b). It also has ethnoveterinary applications in Scandinavia (Cumo 2013). *C. foliosum* (svinski yagodi) aerial decoctions are traditionally used as immunostimulants, antioxidants, and in cancer treatment (Nedialkov et al. 2012; Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011). *C. quinoa* (quinoa) seeds provide high-quality protein with a balanced amino acid profile, and its saponins exhibit biopesticidal and anti-oral pathogen activities (Woldemichael and Wink 2001; Castillo-Ruiz et al. 2018; Sun et al. 2019). Other species also show diverse pharmacological effects: *C. hybridum* L. is used as an analgesic and demonstrates anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory, anti-hyaluronidase, and anti-proliferative activities (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2009; Nowak et al. 2016; Podolak et al. 2016), while *C. album* L., found in tropical Asia, has anthelmintic, laxative, diuretic, and tonic properties; its fruit extracts are antipruritic and antinociceptive, and in Vietnam, it treats snakebites, diarrhea, and gonorrhea (Dai et al. 2002; Chi 2012). Finally, species such as *C. strictum*, *C. ambrosioides*, and *C. formosanum* highlight the genus’s ethnopharmacological significance, from anti-inflammatory and antiparasitic effects to hepatoprotective, antioxidant, and UV-protective activities (Ruffa et al. 2002; Yadav et al. 2007; Tsai et al. 2011; Chyau et al. 2015; Chu et al. 2016; Hong et al. 2016).

The widespread uses of the *Chenopodium* genus in traditional medicine have resulted in considerable chemical analyses of the plants and their active principles. *Chenopodium* species have been shown to contain a rich array of primary and secondary metabolites (flavonoids, saponins, terpenes, sterols, alkaloids, and vitamins) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2009). The diversity of the phytochemical compounds underpins a wide spectrum of biological activities reported in the literature, including antioxidant, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, antibacterial, and cytotoxic effects (Nedialkov and Kokanova-Nedialkova 2021).

This review article provides an overview of the biologically active flavonoids and saponins from the genus *Chenopodium*. For its preparation, leading scientific databases were examined, including Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, and others. The review provides an in-depth analysis of the biological activity of 55 compounds (25 flavonoids and 30 saponins) isolated from various representatives of the genus. Where possible, the relationship between chemical structure and bioactivity was analyzed, and data on their quantitative determination are also provided. The article includes two tables in which the flavonoids and saponins are presented according to their aglycones. These tables provide information on the plant species from which the compounds were isolated, the plant part used, the observed biological activity, and the corresponding literature sources. A detailed discussion

of biological activity is presented in the main text. This comprehensive review of biologically active saponins and flavonoids from the genus *Chenopodium* is intended to inspire researchers to continue targeted phytochemical and pharmacological studies in this area—a crucial step toward the development of natural-product-based drugs for the treatment of socially significant diseases.

Flavonoids: biological activities, structure–activity relationships, and quantitative determination

Twenty-five biologically active flavonoids derived from six aglycones (kaempferol, quercetin, gomphrenol, 6-methoxykaempferol, patuletin, and spinacetin) (Fig. 1) have been identified in species of the genus *Chenopodium*. The largest group is that of kaempferol and its glycosides, comprising nine biologically active compounds (1–9) isolated from five representatives of the genus *Chenopodium* (*C. ambrosioides*, *C. formosanum*, *C. murale*, *C. ficifolium*, and *C. quinoa*) (Table 1). The sugar moiety is attached at positions 3 and 7, with 3-O-diglycosides predominating. The second-largest group is quercetin glycosides, comprising four compounds (10–13) isolated from the seeds of *C. quinoa* and *C. formosanum*. The remaining four groups—namely the glycosides of gomphrenol (14–16), 6-methoxykaempferol (17–19), patuletin (20–22), and spinacetin (23–25)—are each represented by three flavonoids, specifically 3-O di-, tri-, and ferulic acid-acylated triglycosides. Gomphrenol glycosides have been detected only in the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, whereas the glycosides of 6-methoxykaempferol, patuletin, and spinacetin have been isolated both from *C. foliosum* and from the roots and aerial parts of *C. bonus-henricus* (wild spinach). The biologically active flavonoids in the genus *Chenopodium* exhibit diverse biological activities, including cardiovascular, radical-scavenging and antioxidant, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, hMAO-A/B inhibitory, anti- α -glucosidase, prolipase, and anti-adipogenic effects. The available literature also encompasses studies on structure–activity relationships and quantitative determinations of individual compounds, where reported, and these aspects will be critically analyzed and discussed in the present review.

Flavonoids with cardiovascular activity

Kaempferitrin 2 was isolated from the aerial parts of *C. murale* growing in Egypt and was also identified in two other *Chenopodium* species from the same region (*C. ambrosioides* and *C. ficifolium*). An *in vivo* biological assessment of compound 2 demonstrated dose-dependent hypotension and bradycardia in rabbits. Moreover, in genetically hypertensive rats, kaempferitrin 2 also produced a dose-related reduction in arterial pressure. Experiments on isolated guinea pig atria and aortic strips showed that compound

Figure 1. The main aglycones of biologically active flavonoids from the genus *Chenopodium*.

2 did not block β_1 - or α_1 -adrenoceptors. Quantification of kaempferitrin **2** in these Egyptian *Chenopodium* species revealed that *C. ambrosioides* contained the highest level (2.39 mg/g, 0.24%), whereas *C. murale* (0.16%) and *C. ficifolium* (0.097%) contained lower levels (Gohar and Elmazar 1997).

Flavonoids with radical-scavenging and antioxidant activities

The ethanol extract from dried *C. quinoa* seeds yielded six flavonol glycosides (**3–6** and **10–11**), all of which were evaluated for antioxidant activity using the DPPH assay. The two quercetin 3-glycosides, **10** ($IC_{50} = 10 \mu\text{M}$) and **11** ($IC_{50} = 11 \mu\text{M}$), showed significantly stronger radical-scavenging effects than the kaempferol derivatives **3** ($IC_{50} = 82 \mu\text{M}$), **4** ($IC_{50} = 86 \mu\text{M}$), **5** ($IC_{50} > 100 \mu\text{M}$), and **6** ($IC_{50} > 100 \mu\text{M}$). These results evinced that flavonoids containing free ortho-dihydroxy groups in the B-ring possess superior antioxidant properties compared to those lacking this substitution pattern (Zhu et al. 2001).

The methanol extract from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum* yielded three gomprenol glycosides, **14**, **15** (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011), and **16** (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014a). Their radical-scavenging properties were assessed using the DPPH⁺ and ABTS⁺ assays, with ascorbic acid and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) as positive controls. Compounds **14** and **15** exhibited weak or no DPPH⁺ scavenging activity. Additionally, they showed very similar ABTS⁺ activity (29.22% and 28.30%, respectively), comparable to that of BHT (26.49%), but significantly lower than that of vitamin C (91.60%) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014b). The acylated gomprenol

triglycoside **16** exhibited weak ABTS radical-scavenging activity ($IC_{50} = 141.03 \mu\text{M}$) and almost no DPPH radical-scavenging activity ($IC_{50} = 690.48 \mu\text{M}$). Compound **16** also showed no activity in the ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay and no inhibition of lipid peroxidation of linoleic acid by ferric thiocyanate (LPLAFT) test. Moreover, gomprenol glycosides contain a 6,7-methylenedioxy substituent, which reduces the number of free -OH groups, thereby decreasing antioxidant capacity. Glycosylation of flavonoids decreases their antioxidant activity, which may explain the lower activity of gomprenol triglycoside **16** (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014a).

Nine flavonoids **17–25** were isolated and identified from the methanol extract of the aerial parts of wild spinach (*C. bonus-henricus*) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017). Three of these compounds (**18**, **23**, and **24**) were previously identified in the roots of *C. bonus-henricus* (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2015), while compounds **17**, **20**, and **23** were detected in the aerial parts of *C. foliosum* (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011). The radical-scavenging properties of the nine flavonoids were assessed using DPPH⁺ and ABTS⁺ tests, as well as the LPLAFT method. Patuletin glycosides **20**, **21**, and **22** exhibited the strongest DPPH (85.59%, 85.78%, and 86.07%, respectively) and ABTS (90.27%, 90.64%, and 90.76%, respectively) activities, comparable to those of ascorbic acid (86.46% and 90.79%, respectively). This is likely due to the presence of a 3',4'-ortho-dihydroxy configuration in the B ring, free 5-OH and 7-OH groups, as well as a 4-keto group conjugated with the C2–C3 double bond in the patuletin aglycone, which contributes to its radical-scavenging activity. In contrast, glycosides of spinacetin (**23** and **24**) and 6-methoxykaempferol (**17** and **18**) showed markedly low DPPH activity and relatively high ABTS activity (70.18%–74.41%), which may be

Table 1. Bioactive flavonoids from the genus *Chenopodium*.

Nº	Compound	Plant species (parts used)	Biological activity tested	References
Kaempferol and its glycosides				
1	Kaempferol	<i>C. ambrosioides</i> (leaves) <i>C. formosanum</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH); anti-adipogenic activity	Ghareeb et al. 2016; Chyau et al. 2018
2	Kaempferol-3,7-dirhamnoside (kaempferitrin)	<i>C. ambrosioides</i> (aerial part) <i>C. murale</i> (aerial parts) <i>C. ficifolium</i> (aerial parts)	cardiovascular activity (dose-related hypotension and bradycardia)	Gohar and Elmazar 1997
3	Kaempferol-3-O-[β-D-apiofuranosyl(1'''-2'')-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
4	Kaempferol-3-O-[α-L-rhamnopyranosyl(1'''-2'')-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
5	Kaempferol-3-O-[β-D-apiofuranosyl(1'''-2'')-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl(1''''-6'')]-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
6	Kaempferol-3-O-(2,6-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
7	Kaempferol-3-O-α-L-C ₄ -rhamnosyl-(1'''→2'')-β-D-C ₄ -xylopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. ambrosioides</i> (leaves)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Ghareeb et al. 2016
8	Kaempferol-3-O-α-L-C ₄ -rhamnopyranoside (afzelin)	<i>C. ambrosioides</i> (leaves)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Ghareeb et al. 2016
9	Kaempferol-7-O-α-L-C ₄ -rhamnopyranoside	<i>C. ambrosioides</i> (leaves)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Ghareeb et al. 2016
Quercetin glycosides				
10	Quercetin-3-O-[β-D-apiofuranosyl(1'''-2'')-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl(1''''-6'')]-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
11	Quercetin-3-O-(2,6-di-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH)	Zhu et al. 2001
12	Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside (rutin)	<i>C. formosanum</i> (seeds)	anti-adipogenic activity; anti-glycation end products activity	Chyau et al. 2018; Lin et al. 2024
13	Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside-7-O-rhamnopyranoside	<i>C. formosanum</i> (seeds)	increases collagen production	Lin et al. 2024
Gomphrenol glycosides				
14	Gomphrenol-3-O-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside (gomphrenol-3-O-β-D-gentiobioside) (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011, 2014b; Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a
15	Gomphrenol-3-O-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)[β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→6)]-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS)	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011, 2014b
16	Gomphrenol-3-O-(5'''-O-E-feruloyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl-(1→2)[β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→6)]-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); hepatoprotective activity; hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014a; Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a
6-METHOXYFLAVONOL GLYCOSIDES 6-methoxykaempferol glycosides				
17	6-methoxykaempferol-3-O-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside (6-methoxykaempferol-3-O-β-D-gentiobioside) (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts) <i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); hepatoprotective activity; inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011, 2014b, 2017, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017
18	6-methoxykaempferol-3-O-[β-D-apiofuranosyl(1→2)]-β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots, aerial parts)	hepatoprotective activity; radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2015, 2017, 2021a, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017
19	6-Methoxykaempferol-3-O-(5'''-O-E-feruloyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl(1→2)[β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→6)]-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	hepatoprotective activity, radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS), inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity, anti-α-glucosidase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017
Patuletin glycosides				
20	Patuletin-3-O-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside (patuletin-3-O-β-gentiobioside)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts) <i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); hepatoprotective activity; inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011, 2014b, 2017, 2021a, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017;
21	Patuletin-3-O-[β-apiofuranosyl(1→2)]-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	hepatoprotective activity, radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS), inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity, anti-α-glucosidase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017
22	Patuletin-3-O-(5'''-O-E-feruloyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl(1→2)[β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→6)]-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	hepatoprotective activity, radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS), inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity, anti-α-glucosidase activity.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017, 2021a, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017;
Spinacetin glycosides				
23	Spinacetin-3-O-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside (spinacetin-3-O-β-gentiobioside)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts) <i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots, aerial parts)	radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS); inhibition of LP; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2011, 2014b, 2015, 2017, 2021a, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017;
24	Spinacetin-3-O-[β-apiofuranosyl(1→2)]-β-glucopyranosyl(1→6)-β-glucopyranoside	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots, aerial parts)	radical-scavenging (DPPH, ABTS); inhibition of LP; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity, anti-α-glucosidase activity.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2015, 2017, 2021a, 2021c; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017

Nº	Compound	Plant species (parts used)	Biological activity tested	References
25	Spinacetin-3-O-(5'''-O-E-feruloyl)-β-D-apiofuranosyl(1→2)[β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→6)]-β-D-glucopyranoside (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (aerial parts)	hepatoprotective activity, radical-scavenging activity (DPPH, ABTS), inhibition of LP; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity, anti-α-glucosidase activity; hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect.	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017, 2021a, 2021c, 2025a; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017

Lipid peroxidation (LP).

attributed to the absence of ortho-dihydroxy configuration in the B-ring. Notably, glycosides **19** and **25**, which contain esterified ferulic acid in their structure, exhibited higher DPPH and ABTS antioxidant activity compared to other spinacetin and 6-methoxykaempferol glycosides. This enhanced activity is likely due to the key structural features of ferulic acid: the 3-methoxy and 4-hydroxyl groups on its benzene ring, which help terminate free radical chain reactions, and the carboxylic acid group with an adjacent double bond, which provides additional sites for free radical attack and anchors the molecule to lipid membranes, thereby helping prevent lipid peroxidation. All nine compounds demonstrated either a higher (patuletin glycosides **20**, **21**, **22**) or similar (spinacetin and 6-methoxykaempferol glycosides **23–25** and **17–19**, respectively) inhibitory effect on linoleic acid peroxidation compared to vitamin C (Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2017).

Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov (2021a) developed and validated a UHPLC-HRMS method for the simultaneous quantification of flavonoids in the aerial parts of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus*. The predominant constituents of the flavonoid mixture were the glycosides of spinacetin (**23–25**) and patuletin **21**, with total levels ranging from 2.07 to 4.41 mg/g DW and 1.79 mg/g DW, respectively, expressed as hyperoside equivalents. The total content of the 12 identified flavonoids was 15.12 mg/g DW. In a parallel study, the modified UHPLC-HRMS method was used to quantify eight major flavonoids in the same plant from two populations in Vitosha Mountain (Zheleznitsa and Kumata Hut, Bulgaria). Spinacetin derivatives (**23–25**) and a patuletin derivative (**21**) were once again the predominant compounds. In samples from Kumata Hut, their contents ranged from 0.25% to 0.53%, whereas in samples from Zheleznitsa, they ranged from 0.19% to 0.32% (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021a).

Kaempferol **1** and three of its glycosides, **7**, **8**, and **9**, were isolated from the leaves of *C. ambrosioides*, and their radical-scavenging capacities were evaluated using the DPPH assay. Kaempferol **1** exhibited stronger activity ($SC_{50} = 6.35 \mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to its glycosides **7** ($IC_{50} = 9.41 \mu\text{g/mL}$), **8** ($IC_{50} = 12.45 \mu\text{g/mL}$), and **9** ($IC_{50} = 9.20 \mu\text{g/mL}$). The reduced activity of the mono- and di-glycosylated derivatives (**7** and **8**) relative to the aglycone **1** can be attributed to steric hindrance introduced by the bulky sugar substituent at position 3 of the C-ring, which likely interferes with optimal radical-scavenging capacities. Conversely, the glycosidic substituent at position 7 (A-ring) in compound **9** did not affect the conjugation process between the B-ring, 2,3-unsaturated double bond, and 4-carbonyl group—an arrangement known to be critical for radical-scavenging activity. As a result, compound **9** demonstrated slightly higher activity than **7** and **8** (Ghareeb et al. 2016).

Flavonoids with hepatoprotective activity

The hepatoprotective properties of compounds **16–25** were evaluated using an *in vitro* model of rat hepatocyte damage induced by carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4). The results demonstrated that all flavonoids preserved cell viability and GSH levels, decreased LDH leakage, and reduced lipid damage (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014a; Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2015; Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017). For the acylated flavonol glycoside of gomphrenol (compound **16**), these effects were concentration-dependent, with the highest activity observed at the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, comparable to that of silymarin (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2014a). Glycosides of 6-methoxyflavonol aglycones—6-methoxykaempferol (compounds **17–19**), patuletin (compounds **20–22**), and spinacetin (compounds **23–25**)—significantly increased cell viability twofold (55–63%) compared to the toxic agent CCl_4 (30%). GSH levels nearly doubled, rising from $6 \pm 2.6 \text{ nM/mill cells}$ after CCl_4 treatment to 15 ± 3.2 , 13 ± 3.2 , and $12 \pm 3.2 \text{ nM/mill cells}$, respectively, following the addition of flavonoid glycosides **19**; **18**, **20**, **24**; and **21**. Similarly, LDH leakage and MDA levels were reduced by approximately 50% compared to the effect of the toxic agent alone. The effect of compound **19** was slightly superior to that of silybin, a well-known hepatoprotective and antioxidant agent (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2017).

Flavonoids with neuroprotective activity

The nine flavonoids (**17–25**) isolated from the aerial parts of *C. bonus-henricus* were also evaluated for their neuroprotective potential under conditions of *in vitro* 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA)-induced oxidative stress in rat brain synaptosomes. All compounds exhibited statistically significant neuroprotective effects, with the triglycosides of patuletin, spinacetin, and 6-methoxykaempferol (**22**, **25**, and **19**) showing the highest potency, comparable to that of silybin. They preserved cell viability by 77%, 83%, and 92%, respectively, and this effect is likely attributable to the presence of esterified ferulic acid in their structures, which is known to possess antioxidant properties and the ability to scavenge ROS. GSH levels increased approximately fourfold, from 5 nmol/mg protein after 6-OHDA treatment to 18 nmol/mg protein upon addition of flavonoid **19** and nearly tripled in the presence of the other tested compounds (**17**, **18**, **20–25**) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021c). Compounds **20** and **22–25** were further examined in a model of H_2O_2 -induced oxidative

stress on human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells. The pronounced neuroprotective effects of flavonoids **22** and **25** *in vitro*, observed even at the low concentration of 50 μM , are likely due to the presence of esterified ferulic acid in their structures (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021a).

Gomphrenol glycosides **14** and **16**, isolated from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, together with spinacetin glycoside **25**, were evaluated in several models of induced oxidative stress, including 6-OHDA, *t*-BuOOH, and Fe^{2+} /AA-induced lipid peroxidation, where, at a concentration of 50 μM , they demonstrated significant neuroprotective and antioxidant activities. In the presence of 6-OHDA, compounds **14**, **16**, and **25** preserved synaptosomal viability (by 60%) and GSH levels (by 70%), with effects comparable to those of silybin (70%). Under conditions of *t*-BuOOH-induced oxidative stress in isolated rat brain mitochondria, the same flavonoids preserved GSH levels by 70% and reduced MDA production by 32% for spinacetin glycoside **25** and by 36% and 35% for gomphrenol glycosides **14** and **16**, respectively. In the non-enzymatic Fe^{2+} /AA-induced lipid peroxidation model in rat brain microsomes, compounds **14**, **16**, and **25** decreased MDA production by 43–48%, approaching the effect of silybin (51%). Neuroprotection likely involves MAO-B inhibition, ROS scavenging, membrane stabilization (via reduced MDA), and preservation of GSH levels (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a). Additionally, a UHPLC-HRMS method for quantification of flavonoids **14** and **16** from *C. foliosum* was developed and validated. Analysis revealed that gomphrenol glycosides **14** and **16** comprised 37.1% of the total flavonoid content (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a).

Flavonoids with hMAO-A/B inhibitory activity

Gomphrenol glycosides **14** and **16**, isolated from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, together with spinacetin derivative **25** from *C. bonus-henricus*, demonstrated weak hMAO-A inhibition but good hMAO-B inhibitory activity. The inhibitory effects of compounds **25** (18%), **14**, and **16** (20%) against hMAO-A were compared to those of the classical inhibitor chlorglyline (55%). In contrast, all three flavonoids, **14**, **16**, and **25**, reduced hMAO-B activity by 35%, a level moderately comparable to the 55% inhibition produced by the classical hMAO-B inhibitor selegiline (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a).

Flavonoids with anti- α -glucosidase and pro-lipase activities

All flavonoids **17–25** exhibited anti- α -glucosidase and prolipase activity, as demonstrated by LC-MS analysis measuring the released 4-nitrophenol. Among them, the patuletin triglycosides **21** and **22** showed the strongest inhibitory effect against α -glucosidase ($\text{IC}_{50} = 210 \mu\text{M}$ and 249 μM , respectively), comparable to that of acarbose ($\text{IC}_{50} = 206 \mu\text{M}$). Flavonoids **19**, **22**, and **25**, which contain

an esterified ferulic acid substituent, demonstrated higher inhibitory activity than the corresponding triglycosides. All tested compounds **17–25** exhibited prolipase activity, with the acylated flavonoids (compounds **19**, **22**, and **25**) showing the highest effect. Overall, the results indicate that flavonoids bearing a 3', 4'-ortho-dihydroxy substitution pattern in the B-ring possess the most effective anti- α -glucosidase and prolipase properties. Additionally, esterification with ferulic acid further enhances their activity (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021c).

Flavonoids with anti-adipogenic activity

The seeds of *C. formosanum* yielded kaempferol **1** and rutin **12**, both of which demonstrated notable anti-adipogenic activity in 3T3-L1 adipocytes. The *in vitro* evaluation showed that these flavonoids significantly suppressed the expression of adipogenic genes (PPAR γ , C/EBP α , and SREBP-1c) in adipocytes, resulting in inhibited lipid accumulation, a concentration-dependent decrease in triglyceride levels, and a reduction in glycerol-3-phosphate (GPDH) activity (Chyau et al. 2018).

Flavonoids with anti-aging activity

Recent research on the whole grain of *Chenopodium formosanum* led to the isolation of rutin (**12**), which was found to enhance collagen production, and a quercetin glycoside (compound **13**) capable of reducing advanced glycation end products (AGEs) (Lin et al. 2024).

Saponins: biological activities, structure–activity relationships, and quantitative determination

Thirty biologically active saponins (29 triterpenoid saponins and one steroidal saponin) derived from 15 saponinogens (Figs 2, 3) have been identified in species of the genus *Chenopodium*. The largest groups of triterpenoid saponins are those of phytolaccagenic acid (**37–41**) and 30-normedicagenic acid (**51–54**), isolated from two representatives of the genus *Chenopodium* (*C. quinoa* seeds and husk, as well as the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*) (Table 2). Bidesmosides predominate, with sugar chains linked at the C-3 and C-28 positions. The remaining three groups—namely, the saponins of hederagenin (**29–31**), serjanic acid (**34–36**), and 3 β , 21 α , 28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester (**42–44**)—are each represented by three saponins. The saponins of hederagenin and 3 β , 21 α , 28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester have been detected only in *C. quinoa* (seeds/husk) and *C. album* (aerial parts), respectively, whereas the saponins of serjanic acid have been isolated from both *C. quinoa* and *C. hybridum*. The saponins of oleanolic acid

Table 2. Bioactive saponins from the genus *Chenopodium*.

Nº	Compound	Plant species (parts used)	Biological activity tested	References
TRITERPENOID SAPONINS				
Saponins of oleanolic acid				
26	oleanolic acid-3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranoside (calenduloside E)	<i>C. album</i> (seeds) <i>C. strictum</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity	Chakraborty et al. 2016; Grabowska et al. 2024
27	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl oleanolic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester (chikusetsusaponin IVa)	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds); <i>C. strictum</i> (roots)	antifungal activity; hemolytic activity; cytotoxic activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001; Grabowska et al. 2024
Saponins of 2β-hydroxyoleanolic acid				
28	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-2β-hydroxyoleanolic acid-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester (Bonushenricoside B) (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022
Saponins of hederagenin				
29	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl hederagenin 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	antifungal activity; hemolytic activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001
30	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→4)-β-D-glucopyranosyl-28-O-hederagenin	<i>C. quinoa</i> (husks)	antibacterial activity	Dong et al. 2020
31	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl hederagenin 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds, husks)	antifungal activity; hemolytic activity; antibacterial activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001; Dong et al. 2020
Saponins of bayogenin				
32	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-bayogenin-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022
33	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-bayogenin-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022
Saponins of serjanic acid				
34	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl serjanic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (flowers, fruits, seeds, seed coats); <i>C. hybridum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic (apoptosis-inducing) activity	Kuljanabagavad et al. 2008; Grabowska et al. 2021
35	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl serjanic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (flowers, fruits, seeds, seed coats)	cytotoxic (apoptosis-inducing) activity	Kuljanabagavad et al. 2008
36	3-O-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl (1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl serjanic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester (new compound)	<i>C. hybridum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity	Grabowska et al. 2021
Saponins of phytolaccagenic acid				
37	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl phytolaccagenic acid	<i>C. quinoa</i> (husks)	antibacterial activity	Dong et al. 2020
38	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl phytolaccagenic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds, husks)	antifungal activity; hemolytic activity; antibacterial activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001; Dong et al. 2020
39	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl phytolaccagenic acid (new compound)	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds)	antifungal activity hemolytic activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001
40	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl phytolaccagenic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. quinoa</i> (seeds, husks)	antifungal activity; antibacterial activity	Woldemichael and Wink 2001; Dong et al. 2020
41	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-phytolaccagenic acid-27-oxo-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl	<i>C. quinoa</i> (husks)	antibacterial activity	Dong et al. 2020
Saponins of 3β, 21α, 28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester				
42	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-3β,21α,28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester (chenoalbumoside A)	<i>C. album</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity	Huong et al. 2021
43	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-3β,21α,28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester (chenoalbumoside B)	<i>C. album</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity	Huong et al. 2021
44	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-3β,21α,28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester (chenoalbumoside C)	<i>C. album</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity	Huong et al. 2021
Saponins of 3β, 28-dihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-30-oic acid methyl ester				
45	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-3β,28-dihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-30-oic acid methyl ester (chenoalbumoside D)	<i>C. album</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity	Huong et al. 2021
Saponins of phytolaccagenin				
46	3-O-α-L-arabinopyranosyl-phytolaccagenin-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester (Bonushenricoside A) (new compound)	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022
Saponins of gypsogenin				
47	3β-[(O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl)oxy]-23-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid β-D-glucopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (flowers, fruits, seeds, seed coats)	cytotoxic (apoptosis-inducing) activity	Kuljanabagavad et al. 2008

№	Compound	Plant species (parts used)	Biological activity tested	References
Saponins of 3β-hydroxy-27-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid				
48	3β-[(O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl)oxyl]-27-oxo-olean-12-en-28-oic acid β-D-glucopyranoside	<i>C. quinoa</i> (flowers, fruits, seeds, seed coats)	cytotoxic (apoptosis-inducing) activity	Kuljanabagavad et al. 2008
Saponins of 2β-hydroxygypsogenin				
49	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-2β-hydroxygypsogenin-28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; anti-α-glucosidase activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022
Saponins of medicagenic acid				
50	3-O-β-D-glucuronopyranosyl-medicagenic acid-28-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl(1→4)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl ester	<i>C. bonus-henricus</i> (roots)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hepatoprotective activity; neuroprotective activity; pro-lipase activity	Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b, 2019a, 2021b, 2025b; Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022;
Saponins of 30-normedicagenic acid				
51	3-O-[β-D-glucuronopyranosyl methyl ester]-2β,3β-dihydroxy-30-noroleane-12,20(29)-diene-23,28-dioic acid 28-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl ester (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect	Nedialkov et al. 2012
52	3-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-2β,3β-dihydroxy-30-noroleane-12,20(29)-diene-23,28-dioic acid (new compound)	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect; neuroprotective activity	Nedialkov et al. 2012; Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a
53	3-O-β-glucopyranosyl-2β,3β-dihydroxy-30-noroleane-12,20(29)-diene-23,28-dioic acid 28-O-β-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect; hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect; neuroprotective activity	Nedialkov et al. 2012; Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a
54	3-O-β-glucuronopyranosyl 2β,3β-dihydroxy-30-noroleane-12,20(29)-diene-23,28-dioic acid 28-O-β-glucopyranosyl ester	<i>C. foliosum</i> (aerial parts)	cytotoxic activity; IL-2 production modulatory effect	Nedialkov et al. 2012
STEROID SAPONINS				
Spirostanol-type saponins				
55	Desgalactotigonin	<i>C. album</i> (seeds)	cytotoxic (apoptosis-inducing) activity	Chakraborty et al. 2016

reducing SKW-3 cell viability at relatively low concentrations ($IC_{50} = 14.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$) (Nedialkov et al. 2012).

The oleanolic acid glycoside **26** and the steroidal saponin **55**, both identified in the seeds of *C. album*, were evaluated for their cytotoxic properties. Compounds **26** and desgalactotigonin **55** significantly induced apoptosis in human breast cancer (MCF-7) cells, with IC_{50} values of $11.33 \mu\text{M}$ and $8.27 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. The study further revealed that both compounds blocked the cell cycle at the S phase and inhibited human topoisomerases I and II *in vitro* (Chakraborty et al. 2016).

Six saponins of 2β-hydroxyoleanolic acid, bayogenin, phytolaccagenin, 2β-hydroxygypsogenin, and medicagenic acid (**28**, **32**, **33**, **46**, **49**, **50**) were isolated and identified from the MeOH extract of *C. bonus-henricus* roots. Their cytotoxic properties were assessed across a panel of five human leukemic cell lines representing major hematological malignancies: HL-60 (acute promyelocytic leukemia), SKW-3 and Jurkat E6-1 (T-cell leukemias), and BV-173 and K-562 (chronic myeloid leukemias). Among the tested saponins, compounds **28**, **32**, and **50** demonstrated the highest potency, displaying lower IC_{50} values than the remaining saponins (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b). Additionally, a UHPLC-HRMS method for the simultaneous quantification of the six saponins (**28**, **32**, **33**, **46**, **49**, and **50**) in *C. bonus-henricus* roots was developed and validated by Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov (2021b). The analysis showed that the predominant constituents of the EtOH extract were the glycosides of medicagenic acid (**50**), 2β-hydroxygypsogenin (**49**), and bayogenin (**33**). Their contents reached 15.01%, 3.87%, and 2.41% in the crude EtOH extract and 43.69%, 16.16%, and 10.07% in

the purified EtOH extract, respectively. The total content of the six quantified saponins reached 24.9% in the crude extract and 84.02% in the purified extract (Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2021b).

Two serjanic acid saponins (**34** and **36**) found in the aerial parts of *C. hybridum* were evaluated for their cytotoxicity across a panel of cancer cell lines representing skin, prostate, gastrointestinal, thyroid, and lung malignancies. In all models, the cytotoxic activity of both compounds was dose- and time-dependent. Notably, both saponins were more potent than the reference drug doxorubicin against primary melanoma WM793 cells and the prostate carcinoma cell line PC3. Whereas doxorubicin showed an $IC_{50} > 40 \mu\text{g/mL}$ against WM793, compound **36** displayed an IC_{50} of $17.22 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and compound **34** an IC_{50} of $32.24 \mu\text{g/mL}$. The presence of an additional rhamnose unit linked to the arabinose at C-3 in compound **36** may account for its superior activity in the skin cancer panel (HTB-140, A375, and WM793) compared with compound **34**. In contrast, compound **34** demonstrated greater efficacy against gastrointestinal cancer cell lines (Caco-2, HT29, and HepG2) (Grabowska et al. 2021).

The methanolic extract obtained from the aerial parts of *C. album* yielded saponins, named chenoalbumosides A–D (**42–45**), which were tested in a panel of four human cancer cell lines: HT-29 (colorectal adenocarcinoma), SW480 (colon adenocarcinoma), AGS (stomach gastric adenocarcinoma), and MKN7 (gastric carcinoma). All four compounds exhibited only weak cytotoxic effects, with IC_{50} values exceeding $50 \mu\text{M}$ in each of the tested models and ranging from 46.6 to $71.6 \mu\text{M}$ (Huong et al. 2021).

3, 21, 28-trihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-29-oic acid methyl ester
 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = COOCH_3, R_3 = CH_3$

30-normedicagenic acid

3, 28-dihydroxy-11-oxoolean-12-ene-30-oic acid methyl ester
 $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = COOCH_3$

Figure 3. Sapogenins of biologically active triterpenoid saponins in the genus *Chenopodium*.

Oleanolic acid saponins **26** (also previously identified in *C. album* seeds) and **27** (also found in *C. quinoa* seeds) were isolated from the roots of *C. strictum*. They were evaluated for cytotoxic activity across a diverse panel of human cancer cell lines. Within the prostate cancer panel, both calenduloside E **26** and chikusetsusaponin IVa **27** demonstrated notable potency against PC3 cells, with $IC_{50} = 5.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $45.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, whereas the reference drug doxorubicin exhibited an IC_{50} exceeding $50 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Compound **26** showed only weak activity toward the hormone-negative breast cancer line MDA-MB-231, yet displayed markedly higher cytotoxicity against gastrointestinal Caco-2 cells ($IC_{50} = 2 \mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to doxorubicin ($IC_{50} = 3.4 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Calendulo-

side E **26** also exhibited significant effects in the thyroid cancer models, producing a strong cytotoxic response in metastatic lymph node FTC133 cells after just 24 h of incubation ($IC_{50} = 1.9 \mu\text{g/mL}$), approximately twice as potent as the reference drug ($IC_{50} = 4.0 \mu\text{g/mL}$). In the skin cancer WM793 cell line (primary stage 1 melanoma), both **26** and **27** demonstrated greater activity ($IC_{50} = 2.4 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $IC_{50} = 18.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively) than doxorubicin ($IC_{50} > 40 \mu\text{g/mL}$). The overall higher potency of the monodesmoside **26** compared with the bidesmoside **27** is likely attributable to the presence of a free carboxyl group at C-17 (28-COOH) in its structure. Blocking this functional group with a sugar chain appears to reduce the cytotoxic activity of the molecule (Grabowska et al. 2024).

Saponins with immunomodulatory activity

The four glycosides of 30-normedicagenic acid (**51–54**), isolated from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, exhibited a moderate stimulatory effect on the PHA/PMA-induced release of interleukin-2 (IL-2) in Jurkat E6-1 cells (Nedialkov et al. 2012). In the same experimental model, six triterpene saponins (**28, 32, 33, 46, 49, and 50**) isolated from the roots of *C. bonus-henricus* were evaluated. Among them, compound **32** showed the highest activity, enhancing IL-2 release by 63%, a level comparable to that produced by the reference isopri-nosine (66%) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019b).

Saponins with hepatoprotective activity

The hepatoprotective potential of the purified methanolic extract from *C. bonus-henricus* roots, together with the individual saponins **28, 32, 33, 46, 49, and 50**, was assessed using *in vivo* and *in vitro* models of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatocyte damage. The saponin mixture significantly reduced the cell damage caused by CCl₄ in a concentration-dependent manner, exhibiting protective effects comparable to those of silymarin. Among the isolated saponins, bonushenricoside B **28** demonstrated the strongest influence on cell viability, preserving it by 173% relative to the toxic agent CCl₄ alone. Compounds **49** and **50** possessed the strongest protective effects on GSH level and LDH leakage, preserving GSH level at 300% and reducing LDH leakage by 51% and 52%, respectively. In addition, bonushenricoside A **46** produced the greatest reduction in MDA production (64%), indicating substantial inhibition of lipid peroxidation (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2019a).

Saponins with neuroprotective activity

All six saponins (**28, 32, 33, 46, 49, and 50**), isolated from the roots of wild spinach, were tested *in vitro* in a model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity using isolated rat synaptosomes. Each compound demonstrated significant neuroprotective activity. Among them, the bayogenin saponin **32** exhibited the strongest effect, preserving synaptosomal viability and intracellular GSH levels by 28% and 20%, respectively (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021b). In a subsequent *in vivo* study, compound **50** exhibited a statistically significant neuroprotective effect against rotenone-induced neurotoxicity. It preserved GSH levels by 60% and reduced MDA production by 48%, compared with animals treated with rotenone alone. Histological findings indicate that the medicagenic acid saponin (compound **50**) exerts a pronounced neuroprotective effect in rotenone-induced Parkinsonism in mice, preserving

midbrain histoarchitecture and preventing degenerative and necrotic changes (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025b).

Saponins of 30-normedicagenic acid, compounds **52** and **53**, isolated from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, were evaluated for their neuroprotective potential in a model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity using rat synaptosomes. Both saponins preserved synaptosomal viability by 50% and maintained GSH levels at 60%, compared with the control (pure 6-OHDA). The same compounds were further examined in rat brain mitochondria exposed to *t*-BuOOH as a toxic agent. Under these conditions, saponin **52** reduced MDA production by 25%, while compound **53** achieved a 28% reduction. GSH levels were maintained at 50%, compared with 80% preservation observed for the reference compound silybin. In a model of Fe²⁺/AA-induced lipid peroxidation in rat brain microsomes, saponin **52** decreased MDA formation by 23% and compound **53** by 24% (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a). In addition, a UHPLC-HRMS method for the quantification of saponins **52** and **53** from *C. foliosum* was developed and validated. The results demonstrated that the two 30-normedicagenic acid glycosides, **52** and **53**, together accounted for 43.7% of the total saponin content (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a).

Saponins with hMAO-A/B inhibitory effect

Among the compounds isolated from the aerial parts of *C. foliosum*, two 30-normedicagenic acid saponins (**52** and **53**) demonstrated weak inhibitory activity against MAO-A and a more pronounced effect against MAO-B. While the reference inhibitor chlorgyline reduced MAO-A activity by 55%, compounds **53** and **52** inhibited the enzyme by only 19% and 20%, respectively. In contrast, both saponins decreased MAO-B activity by approximately 30%, compared with the 55% inhibition achieved by the positive control selegiline (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2025a).

Saponins with anti- α -glucosidase and pro-lipase activities

Among the six triterpene saponins **28, 32, 33, 46, 49, and 50**, compounds **28** and **49** showed the strongest inhibitory effects against α -glucosidase, as well as the most pronounced prolipase activity. Quantification of 4-nitrophenol release by LC-MS revealed that the glycoside of 2 β -hydroxygypsogenin **49** suppressed α -glucosidase activity by 30%, while bonushenricoside B **28** achieved 44.1% inhibition, exceeding the activity of the positive control acarbose (36.3%) (Kokanova-Nedialkova et al. 2021b). At a concentration of 200 μ M, bonushenricoside B **28** and saponin **49** enhanced lipase activity by 46.08% and 62.10%, respectively. This finding suggests potential applications of these two compounds in the management of cachexia (Kokanova-Nedialkova and Nedialkov 2022).

Conclusion

Biologically active flavonoids and saponins in the genus *Chenopodium* exhibit considerable chemical diversity and are isolated from various plant parts, including seeds, fruit coats, aerial parts, and roots. Among flavonoids, the largest groups are kaempferol and quercetin glycosides, while smaller groups include glycosides of gompfrenol, 6-methoxykaempferol, patuletin, and spinacetin. Saponins are predominantly triterpenoids (with the largest groups being those of phytolaccagenic and 30-normedicagenic acids) and one steroidal spirostanol, with bidesmosides predominating and sugar chains attached at the C-3 and C-28 positions. These compounds exhibit a wide range of biological activities, which can be grouped into several categories: antioxidant and cellular protection, metabolic regulation (anti-adipogenic, prolipase, and anti- α -glucosidase effects), neuroprotective and cardioprotective activity, hepatoprotection, antibacterial and antifungal activity, and immunomodulatory and cytotoxic effects. Overall, these findings highlight the genus *Chenopodium* as a valuable source of bioactive compounds with significant potential for applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and nutraceutical industries.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

References

- Bhargava A, Rana TS, Shukla S, Ohri D (2005) Seed protein electrophoresis of some cultivated and wild species of *Chenopodium*. *Biologia plantarum* 49: 505–511. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10535-005-0042-5>
- Castillo-Ruiz M, Canon-Jones H, Schlotterbeck T, Lopez MA, Tomas A, Martin RS (2018) Safety and efficacy of quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) saponins derived molluscicide to control of *Pomacea maculata* in rice fields in the Ebro Delta, Spain. *Crop Protection* 111: 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2018.04.016>
- Chakraborty D, Jain CK, Maity A, Ghosh S, Choudhury SR, Jha T, Majumder HK, Mondal NB (2016) *Chenopodium album* metabolites act as dual topoisomerase inhibitors and induce apoptosis in the MCF7 cell line. *Medicinal Chemistry Communications* 7(5): 837–844. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5MD00502G>
- Chi VV (2012) Dictionary of Vietnamese Medicinal Plants. Medicine Publishing House, Hanoi, Vietnam, 526–527 pp.
- Chu C-C, Chen S-Y, Chyau C-C, Fu Z-H, Liu C-C, Duh P-D (2016) Protective effect of Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum*) and its bioactive compounds against carbon tetrachloride-induced liver injury, in vivo. *Journal of Functional Foods* 26: 585–597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2016.08.025>
- Chyau C-C, Chu C-C, Chen S-Y, Duh P-D (2015) Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum*) and its bioactive compounds protect against oxidative stress in human HepG2 cells. *Journal of Functional Foods* 18(A): 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2015.06.025>
- Chyau C-C, Chu C-C, Chen S-Y, Duh P-D (2018) The Inhibitory Effects of Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum*) and its bioactive compounds on adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 adipocytes. *Molecules* 23(7): 1780. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23071780>
- Cumo C (2013) Encyclopedia of Cultivated Plants: From Acacia to Zinnia. Bloomsbury Publishing, Oxford. Encyclopedia of Cultivated Plants – Cumo, Christopher – Bloomsbury Publishing – Torrossa, 456–460.
- Dai Y, Ye WC, Wang ZT, Matsuda H, Kubo M, But PPH (2002) Antipruritic and antinociceptive effects of *Chenopodium album* L. in mice. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 81(2): 245–250. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(02\)00096-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(02)00096-X)
- Dong S, Yang X, Zhao L, Zhang F, Hou Z, Xue P (2020) Antibacterial activity and mechanism of action saponins from *Chenopodium quinoa* Willd. husks against foodborne pathogenic bacteria. *Industrial Crops and Products* 149: 112350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112350>
- Elshafie HS, Camele I, Mohamed AA (2023) A comprehensive review on the biological, agricultural and pharmaceutical properties of secondary metabolites based-plant origin. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(4): 3266. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24043266>

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- Ghareeb MA, Saad AM, Abdou AM, Refahy LA-G, Ahmed WS (2016) A new kaempferol glycoside with antioxidant activity from *Chenopodium ambrosioides* growing in Egypt. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry* 32(6): 3053–3061. <https://doi.org/10.13005/ojc/320626>
- Gohar AA, Elmazar MM (1997) Isolation of hypotensive flavonoids from *Chenopodium* species growing in Egypt. *Phytotherapy Research* 11(8): 564–567. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1573\(199712\)11:8<564::AID-PTR162>3.3.CO;2-C](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1573(199712)11:8<564::AID-PTR162>3.3.CO;2-C)
- Grabowska K, Galanty A, Pecio L, Stojakowska A, Malarz J, Zmudzki P, Zagrodzki P, Podolak I (2024) Selectivity screening and structure–cytotoxic activity observations of selected oleanolic acid (OA)-type saponins from the Amaranthaceae family on a wide panel of human cancer cell lines. *Molecules* 26(3): 772. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29163794>
- Grabowska K, Pecio L, Galanty A, Zmudzki P, Oleszek W, Podolak I (2021) Serjanic acid glycosides from *Chenopodium hybridum* L. with good cytotoxicity and selectivity profile against several panels of human cancer cell lines. *Molecules* 26(16): 4915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26164915>
- Hong Y-H, Huang Y-L, Liu Y-C, Tsai P-J (2016) Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum* Koidz.) water extract and its bioactive components ameliorate dermal damage in UVB-irradiated skin models. *BioMed Research International* 2016: 7368797. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/7368797>
- Huong PTT, Trang DT, Thu VK, Mai NT, Nhiem NX, Yen PH, Tai BH, Kiem PV (2021) Four new triterpene glycosides from the aerial parts of *Chenopodium album* and their cytotoxic activity. *Phytochemistry Letters* 44: 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2021.05.004>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Aluani D, Tzankova V, Nedialkov P (2021a) Simultaneous quantification of the major flavonoids from wild spinach by UHPLC-HRMS and their neuroprotective effects in a model of H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress on SH-SY5Y cells. *Pharmacia* 68(4): 657–664. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.68.e71030>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Bucherl D, Nikolov S, Heilmann J, Nedialkov PT (2011) Flavonol glycosides from *Chenopodium foliosum* Asch. *Phytochemistry Letters* 4(3): 367–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2011.08.002>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Kondeva-Burdina M, Nedialkov P (2021b) Saponins from the roots of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. with neuroprotective and anti- α -glucosidase activities. *Pharmacia* 68(2): 387–392. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.68.e64425>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Kondeva-Burdina M, Nedialkov PT (2021c) Neuroprotective, anti- α -glucosidase and pro-lipase active flavonoids from Good King Henry (*Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L.). *Natural Product Research* 35(23): 5484–5488. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2020.1784172>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Kondeva-Burdina M, Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Bucherl D, Nikolov S, Heilmann J, Nedialkov PT (2014a) A New Acylated Flavonol Glycoside from *Chenopodium foliosum*. *Records of Natural Products* 8(4): 401–406. <https://acgpubs.org/doc/2018080915422255-RNP-1304-306.pdf>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Kondeva-Burdina M, Zheleva-Dimitrova D, Tzankova V, Nikolov S, Heilmann J, Nedialkov PT (2015) 6-Methoxyflavonol glycosides with in vitro hepatoprotective activity from *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* roots. *Natural Product Communications* 10(8): 1377–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1934578X1501000816>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P (2017) Antioxidant properties of 6-methoxyflavonol glycosides from the aerial parts of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. *Bulgarian Chemical Communications* 45(D): 253–258. http://www.bcc.bas.bg/BCC_Volumes/Volume_49_Special_D_2017/BCC2017-49-SE-D-253-258.pdf
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P (2021a) Validated UHPLC-HRMS method for simultaneous quantification of flavonoid contents in the aerial parts of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. (wild spinach). *Pharmacia* 68(3): 597–601. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.68.e69781>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P (2021b) Validated UHPLC-HRMS method for simultaneous quantification of six saponins from the roots of the wild spinach (*Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L.). *Pharmacia* 68(2): 321–325. <https://pharmacia.pensoft.net/article/63722/>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P (2022) UHPLC-HRMS based saponin and flavonoid profiling of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. roots and pro-lipase activity of the main saponins. *Proceedings of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences* 75(7): 982–991. <https://doi.org/10.7546/CRABS.2022.07.06>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P, Kondeva-Burdina M, Simeonova R, Tzankova V, Aluani D (2017) *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. – A source of hepatoprotective flavonoids. *Fitoterapia* 118: 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2017.02.001>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov P, Kondeva-Burdina M, Simeonova R (2019a) Hepatoprotective activity of a purified methanol extract and saponins from the roots of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C A Journal of Biosciences* 74(11–12): 329–337. <https://doi.org/10.1515/znc-2019-0002>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov PT, Momekov G (2019b) Saponins from the roots of *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. *Natural Product Research* 33(14): 2024–2031. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2018.1483928>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov PT, Nikolov SD (2009) The Genus *Chenopodium*: phytochemistry, ethnopharmacology and pharmacology. *Pharmacognosy Reviews* 3(6): 280–306. <https://www.phcogrev.com/PharmacognRev-3-6-280>
- Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Nedialkov PT, Nikolov SD (2014b) Pharmacognostic investigations of the aerial parts of *Chenopodium foliosum* Asch. and radical-scavenging activities of five flavonoids isolated from methanol extract of the plant. *Pharmacognosy Journal* 6(4): 43–48. <https://doi.org/10.5530/pj.2014.4.6>
- Kondeva-Burdina M, Panayotova D, Nedialkov PT, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z (2025a) Flavonoids and saponins from two *Chenopodium* species (*C. foliosum* Asch. and *C. bonus-henricus* L.)—preliminary evaluation for hMAO-A/B, neuroprotective activity, and validated UHPLC-HRMS quantification of ethanolic extract from *C. foliosum*. *Molecules* 30(5): 1061. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30051061>
- Kondeva-Burdina M, Panayotova D, Sharkov M, Popov G, Manov V, Nedialkov PT, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z (2025b) *In vivo* evaluation of purified methanolic extract and medicagenic acid saponin from *Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L. roots in a rotenone-induced Parkinson's disease model. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e175172>
- Kuljanabhadgavad T, Thongphasuk P, Chamulitrat W, Wink M (2008) Triterpene saponins from *Chenopodium quinoa* Willd. *Phytochemistry* 69(9): 1919–1926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2008.03.001>
- Lin Y-Y, Lin Y-K, Lin Y-H, Chiang C-F (2024) Novel compounds of Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum* Koidz) increases collagen, antioxidants, inhibits adipogenesis. *Natural Product Research* 38(16): 2763–2772. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2023.2235064>
- Nedialkov PT, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z (2021) Bioactive compounds of Goosefoot (Genus *Chenopodium*). *Bioactive Compounds in Underutilized Vegetables and Legumens* 97–119. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57415-4_7
- Nedialkov PT, Kokanova-Nedialkova Z, Bucherl D, Momekov G, Heilmann J, Nikolov S (2012) 30-Normedicagenic acid glycosides from

- Chenopodium foliosum*. Natural Product Communications 7(11): 1419–1422. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1934578X1200701104>
- Nowak R, Szewczyk K, Gawlik-Dziki U, Rzymowska J, Komsta L (2016) Antioxidative and cytotoxic potential of some *Chenopodium* L. species growing in Poland. Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences 23(1): 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2015.01.017>
- Podolak I, Olech M, Galanty A, Zaluski D, Grabowska K, Sobolewska D, Michalik M, Nowak R (2016) Flavonoid and phenolic acid profile by LC-MS/MS and biological activity of crude extracts from *Chenopodium hybridum* aerial parts. Natural Product Research 30(15): 1766–1770. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2015.1136908>
- Ruffa MJ, Ferraro G, Wagner ML, Calcagno ML, Campos RH, Cavallaro L (2002) Cytotoxic effect of Argentine medicinal plant extracts on human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line. Journal of Ethnopharmacology 79(3): 335–339. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-8741\(01\)00400-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-8741(01)00400-7)
- Sun X, Yang X, Xue P, Zhang Z, Ren G (2019) Improved antibacterial effects of alkali-transformed saponin from quinoa husks against halitosis-related bacteria. BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies 19: 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-019-2455-2>
- Tsai P-J, Chen Y-S, Sheu C-H, Chen C-Y (2011) Effect of nanogrinding on the pigment and bioactivity of Djulis (*Chenopodium formosanum* Koidz.). Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 59(5): 1814–1820. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf1041273>
- Woldemichael GM, Wink M (2001) Identification and biological activities of triterpenoid saponins from *Chenopodium quinoa*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 49(5): 2327–2332. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0013499>
- Yadav N, Vasudeva N, Singh S, Sharma SK (2007) Medicinal properties of genus *Chenopodium* Linn. Natural Product Radiance 6(2): 131–134. p106–107.p65
- Zhu N, Sheng S, Li D, Lavoie EJ, Karwe MV, Rosen RT, Ho C-T (2001) Antioxidative flavonoid glycosides from quinoa seeds (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.). Journal of Food Lipids 8: 37–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4522.2001.tb00182.x>